

Climateurope2

Intermediate assessment of organised activities and second update to the community engagement strategy

Deliverable 6.3

Authors: Marjana Brkic (CPN), Ljubica Slavkovic (CPN), Judith Klostermann (WR), Andreas Villwock (HEREON), Stacey New (MettOffice), Inés Martin del Real (BSC)

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101056933.

Document Information

Grant agreement	No 101056933
Project title	Supporting and standardising climate services in Europe and beyond
Project acronym	Climateurope2
Project start date	01/09/2022
Related work package	WP6
Related task(s)	T6.1, T6.2
Lead organisation	CPN
Authors	Marjana Brkic (CPN), Ljubica Slavkovic (CPN), Judith Klostermann (WR), Andreas Villwock (HEREON), Stacey New (MetOffice), Inés Martin del Real (BSC)
Submission date	31/05/2025
Dissemination level	Public

History

Date	Submitted by	Reviewed by	Vision (notes)
25/04/2025	Ljubica Slavkovic	WP6 team and consortium	
5/5/2025	Ljubica Slavkovic	Kevin Ramírez (CLIMATE-KIC)	Final review

Please cite this report as: Brkic, M., Slavkovic, L., Klostermann, J.E.M, New, S., Villwock, A., Martin del Real, I. (2025), Intermediate assessment of organised activities and second update to the community engagement strategy, D6.3 of the Climateurope2 project

Disclaimer: Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

1 Introduction	6
1.1 Aims of the D6.3 Intermediate assessment of organised activities and second update to the community engagement strategy	7
2 Current status of the Climateurope2 network	9
3 Channels for engagement	11
3.1 Climateurope2 project website	11
3.2 Climateurope2 platform	12
3.3 Social media	14
3.4 Proposal for future use of channels	15
4 Events for engagement	16
4.1 Climateurope2 webinars	16
4.2 Webstivals and Festivals	17
4.3. Roadshow	18
4.4. Sessions and side events in other conferences	20
5 Interaction with other projects	21
6 Involvement of WPs in community engagement	25
7 Methods to monitor progress of the network	27

List of tables

Table 1. An example of utilizing the Climateurope2 platform

Table 2. Held webinars

Table 3. Completed Roadshow

Table 4. Conferences with relevance for the Climateurope2 network

Table 5. Relevant projects from the Grant Agreement

Table 6. Active Sister projects

Table 7. WP6 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Table 8. WP6 Deliverables

List of figures

Figure 1. Climateurope2 network density map showing the worldwide location of network members

Figure 2. Climateurope2 network density map - focus on Europe

Figure 3. Homepage button to join the network

Figure 4. Communication vectors that are used in Climateurope2

Figure 5. Climateurope2 YouTube channel

Figure 6. Community building roadmap: internal and external strategy

Figure 7. Task 6.1 legend

Figure 8. Task 6.2 legend

About Climateurope2

Timely delivery and effective use of climate information is fundamental for a green recovery and a resilient, climate neutral Europe, in response to climate change and variability. Climate services address this through the provision of climate information for use in decision-making to manage risks and realise opportunities.

The market and needs for climate information has seen impressive progress in recent years and is expected to grow in the foreseeable future. However, the communities involved in the development and provision of climate services are often unaware of each other and lack interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary knowledge. In addition, quality assurance, relevant standards, and other forms of assurance (such as guidelines, and good practices) for climate services are lagging behind. These are needed to ensure the saliency, credibility, legitimacy, and authoritativeness of climate services, and build two-way trust between supply and demand.

Climateurope2 aims to develop future equitable and quality-assured climate services to all sectors of society by:

- Developing standardisation procedures for climate services
- Supporting an equitable European climate services community
- Enhancing the uptake of quality-assured climate services to support adaptation and mitigation to climate change and variability

The project identifies the support and standardisation needs of climate services, including criteria for certification and labelling, as well as the user-driven criteria needed to support climate action. This information will be used to propose a taxonomy of climate services, suggest community-based good practices and guidelines, and propose standards where possible. A large variety of activities to support the communities involved in European climate services will also be organised.

Executive Summary

The first Climateurope project, active between 2016 and 2021, established a broad network comprising representatives from academia, NGOs, businesses, governments, and the public, with 388 members from 40 countries. With the start of Climateurope2, all members were individually consulted about sharing their contact information for the new project, and 84 of them joined the Climateurope2 network initially (data provided by WP7 in November 2022).

Climateurope2 aims to expand and diversify the climate services community, in which Work Package 6 has an important task. The goal is to involve more members, in particular from southern and eastern European countries, and outside the academic community, for example, from private organizations, governments and NGOs. Various engagement methods, including social media, Festivals, and webinars, were applied to enlarge the climate services community. After 5 webinars, 4 Webstivals, one festival and roadshows at five locations in SEE (Southeastern Europe), as well as appearances at several major conferences such as the European Climate Change Adaptation (ECCA) conference, the Climateurope2 network comprises **480** (Information provided by WP7 in March 2025) members. Climateurope2 focuses on bolstering external initiatives to enhance community growth and engagement, evident in the substantial increase in community numbers before and after events such as the first two roadshows in June 2024, where membership rose from 259 to 304 participants.

Deliverable 6.3 “Intermediate assessment of organised activities and second update to the community engagement strategy” gives a brief overview of the activities held, and channels used and the response in community engagement that they induced.

Keywords

Climate services community, Climateurope2 network, engagement strategy, events, platform, social media, diversity, equity and inclusiveness

1 Introduction

Climate services are a fast-developing field. Consultancy and government climate services aid users in managing and avoiding climate risks and seizing opportunities to adapt to climate change. Despite recent development and projected growth of the climate service market, doubts persist about the scientific quality and user suitability of climate services. Existing quality assurance methods like [WMO guidelines](#) are limited in coverage and accessibility, and urgent efforts are needed to establish minimum quality benchmarks for effective climate services. Therefore, Climateurope2 aims to support the development of accessible, effective climate services and to identify what should be the threshold of their minimum quality in an equitable manner for all sectors of society by:

- Developing standardisation procedures for climate services;
- Building an equitable European network for climate services;
- Improving climate services to support adaptation to and mitigation of climate change and climate variability.

This document (D6.3) presents an intermediate assessment of the organised activities and the second update to the community engagement strategy for the Horizon Europe project Climateurope2. It describes the status of the Climateurope2 network, the overview of the implemented activities, as well as the update of the strategy to include more members of the climate services community. A publishable version of this deliverable will be available in M34 (June 2025). For an overview of WP6 deliverables, see Annex 1.

Climateurope2 network: anyone who has registered through the Climateurope2 project website, including individuals with a lower and higher involvement, but all receive the communications from the project through the mailing list.

Climate services community: everyone involved with climate services as producers, users, and those in the intersection of the two, partly involved in the Climateurope2 network and partly not yet involved.

Neither the community nor the network are static entities. The climate services community will grow autonomously. Climateurope2 aims to enhance this growth by bringing the actors needed for standardising and for improving the quality of climate services into the community. We also aim to grow the Climateurope2 network of active participants.

This intermediate assessment will contribute to the aims of Climateurope2, namely, to strengthen the climate services community. WP6 aims to promote an open exchange of knowledge, expertise and data among the climate services community to identify:

- Existing standards and remaining gaps in standardisation;
- Usable and effective labelling and certification;
- Good practices in climate services;
- Economic, social and environmental values of using climate services;

- Current market of CS, its gaps and possible future developments;
- Decision-making and policy support requirements.

WP6 is also promoting networking and exchange within the community, supporting market development and assisting other work packages in their exchanges with the climate services community.

1.1 Aims of the D6.3 Intermediate assessment of organised activities and second update to the community engagement strategy

The aims of the community engagement strategy (from Grant Agreement part A):

- Establish, further develop and monitor the Climateurope2 network;
- Identify gaps in the diversity of the participants of this European climate service network
- Improve the representation of different stakeholder typologies from the public and private sectors;
- Reach a greater inclusion from under-represented regions (e.g. Eastern Europe);
- Enhance the attainment of a diverse and inclusive community.
- Actively engage community members in the activities of the Climateurope2 project
- Bring the community together, enhance knowledge exchange between community members, and build links across the climate services value chain.
- Connect the Climateurope2 network to participatory processes in the project WPs, doing it in a structured and optimised way.

The strategy uses two main ways to organise interaction: communication channels and events. Communication channels are organised by WP7 and WP6 makes use of them for growing the community. Regarding the channels, three types are used for interaction:

- The Climateurope2 project website is a public medium to inform anyone interested in the aims, progress, activities and results of the Climateurope2 project and where the climate services community can share information about other relevant initiatives.
- A Climateurope2 platform is created where the Climateurope2 network members can engage with other people working with climate services, participate in discussions about good practices, guidelines, find and share useful resources for climate change adaptation and mitigation, and access the most relevant results of the project.
- Social media channels, such as LinkedIn and Twitter, are used in the project to engage with several audiences, and also the Climateurope2 network.

There are several types of events organised for interaction with the network to share knowledge, opinions, experiences and to widen the network:

- A webinar series with stakeholders' perspectives, which are of interest of different audiences, including the private sector

- Invited webinars from other projects and initiatives
- Webstivals (online festivals) and festivals
- A Roadshow visiting different countries across South East Europe (SEE).
- Business breakfasts targeting standardisation and certification institutions and other business stakeholders.
- Sessions and side events in other conferences such as the meeting of the European Meteorological Society ([EMS](#)), the 8th [ENES HPC](#) (European Network for Earth System Modelling - High Performance Computing) workshop.
- Sessions and side events in selected business arenas and conferences; the private sector needs specific engagement activities, also through intermediaries

In addition to utilizing communication channels and events, WP6 facilitates interactions with sister projects to expand and strengthen the network of climate services. It also fosters relationships with interested institutions to explore opportunities for further utilization of the project's outcomes. WP6 extended invitations to several sister projects to participate in the agendas of two Webstivals and one Festival. Furthermore, WP6 assists by creating connections between WPs 1-5 and the climate services community. Throughout the project timeline, we aim to understand their needs, for meeting standardisation requirements, and for knowledge exchange that can further equip all the work and activities of the project. Involvement of the community is critical for understanding standardisation needs and is therefore needed for providing information to key deliverables, for example, WP1. All WPs have direct contacts with members of the climate services community through the mailing lists, and these interactions are expected to grow as the project progresses. WP6 offers expertise and support for new and/or better interaction. Discussions with WPs 1-5 were periodically organised to define specific aims and targets.

Throughout all the project activities, WP6 is monitoring the network's diversity, equity and inclusiveness. Furthermore, other aspects are monitored, such as regional gaps (e.g. in terms of EU Member States or European countries), gender balance, age (e.g. youth engagement), and gaps in sectors or organisation types.

2 Current status of the Climateurope2 network

Since its inception in 2022, Climateurope2 has established a network of 480 members, which include a range of actors involved in the climate services value chain (e.g. providers, intermediaries, end-users and interested parties), spanning across sectors and countries worldwide. The efforts to broaden community representation are ongoing, with 170 members from 5 Southeast European countries. This document tracks the network's growth and introduces an updated engagement strategy aimed at enhancing member participation through activities, events and channels such as Climateurope2 platform.

The network provides a resource for knowledge sharing for climate service users and providers across Europe, and to some extent, beyond. Figure 1 shows the global coverage of the Climateurope2 project with network members joining from as far afield as Australia, Africa and South America. New members can easily join via the CE2 Webpage, and BSC (WP7) keeps track and provides all community member data, including member count, countries, sectors, and personal information.

CE2 network distribution

Figure 1. Climateurope2 network density map showing the worldwide location of network members (updated May 2025).

CE2 network distribution

Figure 2. Climateurope2 network density map - focus on Europe (updated May 2025).

A growing, active climate services network is key for achieving the main objectives of the Climateurope2 project, and developing the climate service network across Europe is a main objective of WP6. From May 2024 until March 2025, the Climateurope2 network has grown rapidly. Due to active involvement of the community throughout different activities (see chapter 4), the community now comprises **480 members** spanning different sectors and coming from different backgrounds. The majority of the Climateurope2 network members come from academia (153 members), followed by the private sector (124), and the public sector (116), while the NGOs (52) and other (35) count the lowest number of members. Initially, Climateurope2 had a higher proportion of members from academia. However, by hosting webstivals tailored to the private sector (as outlined in chapter 4.2), the number of private sector members has increased substantially. By hosting dedicated webinars, festivals, and activities targeting specific topics and groups, it is expected that the community members from other sectors will grow as well. This aims to expand the community while achieving a balanced representation across sectors. Additionally, to reach the audience in European countries that currently have a low representation, activities like the roadshow are targeted, in particular in the SEE region. To ensure gender balance throughout all activities, WP6 has developed Guidelines for engaging with users in workshops, capacity building, and other interactions (M6.1), which led to nearly equal representation of genders, achieving a balanced ratio of almost 50/50, with a slightly higher female representation. Following the first five roadshows, the community grew from 260 to 418 members, with a total of 158 new members. Notably, 103 of these new members are from Eastern Europe.

Climateurope2 aims to amplify the climate service community, for example, by developing standardization procedures and guidelines to ensure equitable, quality-assured, and user-relevant

climate services. This is the case not only for standardisation organisations but also for others such as organisations that provide guidance to companies in reporting climate change risk, such as the TCFD¹. Also, the specific focus on standardisation of Climateurope2 should reach out to those who are not using climate services yet but for whom improved quality and usability of climate services would make them more attractive. WP6 will assist in further development of the network by organising events, contributing to communication channels, interacting with other WPs and with other Horizon Europe projects, as described in the next chapters.

3 Channels for engagement

This chapter explains the role of the project website, the interactive platform, and social media in engaging existing and new community members in Climateurope2. These communication channels are managed by WP7, while WP6 actively utilizes them.

3.1 Climateurope2 project website

The Climateurope2 project website, launched in October 2022 by Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC), serves as a central hub for all project-related information at <https://climateurope2.eu/>. It offers visibility and accessibility to project information and external communication. Updated within the reporting period, the project homepage has been rearranged to make events and news more visible (at the top of the page). A new section named 'Network' has been created with a map that shows the distribution of the CE2 network members per country. This visualisation helps to easily and visually grasp whether the network is developing in an equitable way across regions. Moreover, additional material has been added to the already existing sections of the website.

Figure 3. Homepage button to join the network

¹ Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures: <https://www.fsb-tcfd.org/>

Managing the project website is a task of WP7 (Task 7.1); however, other WPs provide content for the website. The climate services community can share information about other relevant initiatives which are shared under “Events” at the News & events page of the website: <https://climateurope2.eu/news-events/events>. If any of the external events are of high relevance, they also appear in the ‘News and Events’ section of the homepage, which lists the three most relevant events and news.

Present options and statistics for interaction and connectivity through the website:

- The homepage features a network join button, enabling members to participate and receive information in all project activities and receive updates. The form for joining states that Climateurope2 will use the provided information to stay in touch regarding project updates. BSC maintains the personal contact list. The homepage is updated regularly with project highlights, including events, podcasts, newsletters, deliverables, and milestones.
- So far, Climateurope2 has published three newsletters. Currently, 196 people subscribed to the newsletter. Subscriptions are possible through the homepage. Note, that subscription to the network and to the newsletter are managed separately.
- Through the contact form on the website visitors can ask questions or send comments to the project team. The team at BSC can also be contacted directly through the email address: infoclimateurope2@bsc.es. WP7 monitors visits to the website by Google analytics. From May 2024 to March 2025 2.400 visits were registered.
- The website has a section for upcoming events, including both project-organised and other relevant events related to climate services organised by other projects or partners. Thus, the portal acts as a hub for the community to find relevant information.

The growing engagement across Climateurope2 channels reflects the effectiveness of the community engagement strategy since the project's inception.

3.2 Climateurope2 platform

WP7 Task 7.4 has developed the Climateurope2 platform, exclusive to Climateurope2 network members. For an overview of the project communication flow and the platform's position, see Fig. 3. Upon joining the Climateurope2 network, members gain access to the platform through which they can engage with peers, discuss best practices, access resources for climate change adaptation and mitigation, search for relevant documents, and visualise climate services-related information. An internal webinar for the consortium on how to use the platform was organised in May 2024. Initially, the platform is tested and used by the consortium internally before it will be opened up to the external CE2 network.

The beta version of the platform, available at <https://ce2-platform-beta.maris.nl/>, has been tested through interviews with various project partners. The insights obtained through these interactions have led to adjustments of the platform design and upgrades for better useability, including improved

onboarding and navigation, tooltips, intuitive landing pages, and glossary cards for clearer messaging. The platform integrated several features to enhance communication among users. Communication is further supported by improved commenting and versioning systems, where users can see which document version comments refer to. Notification systems have been enhanced: users are notified by email when added as collaborators or when comments or access requests occur. AI-generated summaries help users quickly understand dashboard content, aiding in information sharing.

The platform will be fully operational in August 2025, and its official launch will take place during the second Climateurope2 Festival in Belgrade from September 29th to October 1st. A hands-on session will be organised during the Festival to showcase some of the functionalities (e.g. visual analytics dashboard) and to encourage attendees to join the ‘Network’ section. To support the platform's public launch a dissemination strategy is planned, including a promotional video.

Figure 4. Communication vectors that are used in Climateurope2

The platform is a hub for the engagement of members of the Climateurope2 network to discuss best practices and gather feedback on climate service issues. At the moment, CE2 consortium partners use the platform to share project documents and collect feedback from other partners. Examples of the use of the platform by the CE2 consortium are described in Table 1 below. Once it is launched, the platform will be open to the CE2 network for wider use.

Table 1. An example of utilizing the Climateurope2 platform

Work package	Platform use
--------------	--------------

WP1	Inclusion of the synthesis report (the ongoing synthesis of all WPs, which includes 3 milestones prior to the final deliverable in month 52).
WP2	Sharing a preliminary version of best practices and the current state-of-the-art in the second stage of each task (halfway to the project).
WP3	A review of deliverable D3.3 through the platform in the third year. Discuss lessons learnt for the final deliverable D3.4.
WP4	Publish the state of the market on the platform three times (M14 (D4.2) and two updates in M28 (D4.5) and M48 (D4.10)). Share outputs of Task 4.4.

3.3 Social media

Social media channels are used in the project to engage with several audiences, including members of the Climateurope2 network. The usefulness of social media platforms for interactive functions is mainly to create engagement and acquire new network members through the promotion of the project itself, its outputs, and the activities that are organised.

Climateurope2 developed communities on LinkedIn and X (previously Twitter), and at the end of 2024 also included BlueSky. The new CE2 Bluesky account (<https://bsky.app/profile/climateurope2.bsky.social>) has been launched in addition to the previously existing social media channels used by the project (LinkedIn, X and YouTube). This new network is being explored as an alternative to X. However, the CE2 X account is still active since we have a large community that was inherited from the former Climateurope project. Maintenance of the LinkedIn, X, and Bluesky accounts is part of Task 7.1.

While social media is managed and tracked by WP7, it is useful to have an overview of the build-up of followers and engaged users, as it is another indicator for the growth of the Climateurope2 network. By April 2025, Climateurope2's X (x.com/climateurope2) account had 2.380 followers. Climateurope2's BlueSky account (<https://bsky.app/profile/climateurope2.bsky.social>) launched end of 2024 and has grown to 32, while its LinkedIn page (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/climateurope2/>) now has 1.182 followers compared to 648 at May 2024. Climateurope2 YouTube channel (see figure below) (<https://www.youtube.com/@climateurope2609>), with 53 subscribers, 97 videos published, 3,100 views, +53 followers, 3 podcast episodes and 48k impressions, serves as a repository for project-related recordings, including Festivals and Webstivals.

Figure 5. Climateurope2 YouTube channel

3.4 Proposal for future use of channels

The cooperation between WP6 and WP7 has been very fruitful. Together with other work packages, WP6 produces a significant share of content for the website. The subscription link helps to grow the community and to do this within GDPR guidelines. The Climateurope2 platform is still in the testing phase and WP6 events can be used to promote it and invite users.

The website will continue to showcase the project's activities through new articles, event announcements, and a blog. The blog is open to contributors outside the project, providing a space to share views on the needs for climate services and their standardisation in Europe, fostering discussion and reflection on the topic. As before, all website publications will also be shared through our social media channels.

We aim to grow our followers and engagement on social media, especially on our new Bluesky account. However, this will depend on how the climate community evolves across different platforms following the major shift away from X (formerly Twitter).

4 Events for engagement

4.1 Climateurope2 webinars

At least 6 webinars delivered by representatives from the climate service community to grasp how they respond to the project's outcomes and identify opportunities will be organized in total during the Climateurope2 project. To date, 5 webinars have been conducted: one by the University of Leeds and BSC focusing on UK climate services standards and value (November 3, 2022), the second jointly organised by Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change (CMCC) and Center for the Promotion of Science (CPN) addressing the Art and science towards climate action (May 25, 2023), while the third addressed the uncertainty in communication on climate services, organised by UKRI – UK Research and Innovation (November, 30, 2023). On June 21, 2024, a Stakeholders' Perspectives webinar took place, organized by BSC and moderated by DNV-BSC, focusing on the views of the private sector. It featured experts from the energy and insurance industries, including EDP Renewables and AXA XL. On November 5, 2024, another Stakeholders' Perspectives webinar took place, organized by BSC, focusing on the views of journalists and the communication sector. Speakers in the stakeholders' perspectives webinars are often members of the Climateurope2 network.

Table 2. Held webinars

Date	Title	Speaker/Organization
3 November 2022	UK climate services standards and value	University of Leeds, BSC
25 May 2023	Art and science towards climate action	Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change (CMCC), Center for the Promotion of Science (CPN)
30 November 2023	Uncertainty in communication on climate services	UKRI – UK Research and Innovation
21 June 2024	Stakeholders' Perspectives webinar - Private sector	BSC, DNV-BSC
5 November 2024	Stakeholders' Perspectives webinar - Communication and journalism sector	BSC

All webinars were recorded and uploaded to the project website in compliance with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) regulations. The next stakeholders' perspectives webinar is being

planned for June 2025, around the topic of urban planning and equity. The webinars are stakeholder-targeted including salient topics and narratives which are of interest for different audiences, including the private sector, all in the aim of fostering community engagement and its continuous growth.

○ 4.2 Webstivals and Festivals

So far, WP6, under the leadership of CMCC organised four Webstivals in M6, M12, M24 and M31. Two more Webstivals are planned to be organised throughout the project timeline (M45, M52). The first two webstivals were detailed in the D6.2 document. CMCC led the organisation of the webstivals, with all partners and work packages contributing.

[The third Climateurope2 webstival](#) focused on Climate Innovation and Standardization and convened policymakers, entrepreneurs, researchers, and climate experts to address current challenges in climate services. Featuring **356 registered participants, 211 actively engaged participants** and **35 speakers** over the two-day programme, key themes included defining and improving climate services, financial protection, health and water sustainability, storytelling and communication, innovation and digital tools for climate adaptation, and planning future events focused on climate action and city mitigation.

[The fourth Climateurope2 webstival](#) addressed Climate Services for Cities. The focus was on the innovative approaches in the context of new EU or national projects and activities related to climate adaptation in urban areas were discussed. A total of **518 participants** registered for the webstival, with **283 actively engaging** over the two-day programme. Key themes included the foundational role of climate services in both adaptation and mitigation, their application in urban contexts, new national initiatives, digital innovation such as the Climate Digital Twins, and the importance of equity, power dynamics, and inclusion in climate services.

The first Climateurope2 in-person event was the Festival organised on 11-13 March 2024 in Venice, Italy. Titled "Bridging science, services and standards for a climate-resilient future", it incorporated four overarching themes - urban and water management and challenges, EU mission on climate change, and Communicating climate knowledge - Bridging the gap and gathered over 100 participants on-site. More details on this topic were presented in the Deliverable 6.2.

The second Climateurope2 in-person event is the [Festival](#) planned to take place in Belgrade, Serbia, September 29 - October 1, 2025. The organization of the event is performed by WP6, the local organization is led by CPN. Amongst other topics, the 2nd Climateurope2 festival seeks to foster the representation of southeastern European countries, e.g. through special sessions and topics and by providing support for participants from this region to attend.

The local arrangements were presented and discussed with the consortium partners at the WP6 meetings dedicated to the Festival, as well as at the monthly management board meetings. A dedicated Festival Committee was established. The key aspects related to the organization and structure of the festival, the coordination of the General Assembly, and the development of accompanying programmes related to art+science were initiated. In addition, in collaboration with WP7, preparations for

communication and promotional materials started, with the first advertisement, such as posters and “save the date” website news, were published.

○ 4.3 Roadshow

The CE2 roadshow is a series of smaller events happening in different countries across South East Europe (SEE). Its aim is to promote the Climateurope2 network in the region of SEE, through local stakeholder engagement in their native languages. The roadshow - so-called “travelling climate action” - is set to tour 10 locations in SEE from M10 to M48. The first part of the “travelling climate action” was carried out visiting [five locations](#): Rijeka (Croatia), Tirana (Albania), Kotor (Montenegro), Sarajevo and Skopje (North Macedonia).

The first in a series of events was realized from June 19 to 21 in Rijeka (Croatia), in cooperation with the Faculty of Physics of the University of Rijeka, while the event in Tirana (Albania), which took place on June 24 and 25, was the result of the cooperation of CPN with organizations Serbian Gaming Association and Albanian Gaming Community from Tirana. The last three locations were Kotor (Montenegro) in cooperation with Marine Biology Institute, University of Montenegro from 11th to 14th August; Sarajevo (Bosnia and Herzegovina) from 3rd to 5th October, organized with Verlab Research Institute and on December 5 2024 in Skopje, in partnership with the Faculty of Computer Science and Engineering at the University of St. Cyril and Methodius.

Table 3. Completed Roadshow

Date	Location	Partner
19 - 21 June 2024	Rijeka, Croatia	Faculty of Physics of the University of Rijeka
24 - 25 June 2024	Tirana, Albania	Serbian Gaming Association, Albanian Gaming Community
11 - 14 August 2024	Kotor, Montenegro	Marine Biology Institute, University of Montenegro
3 - 5 October 2024	Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina	Verlab Research Institute
5 December 2025	Skopje, North Macedonia	Faculty of Computer Science and Engineering at the University of St. Cyril and Methodius

Local partners and CPN organized panel discussions on climate services, which brought together those interested in using climate data for smart decision-making. The topics of the panels covered a broad range from local climate issues and climate services, the importance of long-term climate change

monitoring, Adriatic climate modelling, local hydrometeorological service data for users and decision-makers, multidisciplinary research, pollution control technologies, the use of big data for cleaner air, and more. These topics were presented from the perspective of local actors and CPN's team, followed by open discussions.

The five roadshows were attended by more than **200 registered visitors** coming from academia and different stakeholders from the private and public sectors, as well as from the non-governmental organizations and civil society interested in climate services. Following the first five roadshows, the network grew from 260 to 418 members, with a total of **158 new members**. Notably, **103** of these new members are from South Eastern Europe.

The first five roadshows were documented and featured in a [promotional video](#) produced by CPN. The video was published in November 2024.

Additionally, CPN presented the [Climate capsule](#), a mobile and modular installation designed as an intense experience that provides visitors a layered perspective on climate change through scientific facts, art interventions and multimedia content, as well as the winning project of the Climateurope2 open art+science call in 2023 called [M1L3NA](#), an interactive climate storytelling installation, giving each visitor a personal prediction of the future in the context of climate change. Besides M1L3NA, CPN use various artistic pieces and exhibitions alongside the Climate capsule as an innovative way of communicating climate services.

At various locations in the five locations of the roadshows, the "Climate Capsule" attracted visitors from various sectors, calling for climate action through multimedia content describing our planet and the impacts of climate change in the year 2057. Accompanying content included virtual and augmented reality technologies. The "Climate Capsule" was displayed at Korzo in Rijeka and the Faculty of Physics in Rijeka. In Tirana, the public could visit it at the Agimi Art Center and Coolab, in Kotor at the Institute as part of the Kotor Art Festival and, in Sarajevo, passersby could experience it outside the Sarajevo Shopping Center. In Skopje, the "Climate Capsule" was displayed at two locations: Netaville and Base42. While over 200 registered participants attended the five official roadshow panel sessions, more than 1,000 people have so far taken part in various roadshow activities and accompanying events, including individuals from the academia and arts, the private and public sectors, as well as the non-governmental and civil society sectors. By connecting science and art, showcasing art installations and works, organizing artistic performances, and hosting climate discussions in panels, CPN initiated the promotion of climate services to expand the Climateurope2 network.

In addition to the art installations, an informal poetic dialogue took place in Rijeka. Through poetry and photography, an open public call for climate action was presented. At the end of 2024 CPN launched the 2nd open art+science call entitled "*Climate Action Through Poetry and Photography*", as part of the Climateurope2 project. The call invited both professional and amateur poets and photographers from Southeast Europe to creatively respond to the theme of climate change. More than **70 submissions** were received from individuals of various ages and backgrounds—from primary school students to retirees, and from different professional sectors—including entries from Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Slovenia, Montenegro, and North Macedonia. After a thorough evaluation by a

diverse jury, the winning entries were selected: a photography series and a series of poems. The selected works, along with other curated submissions from the call, will be presented at the Climateurope2 Festival in Belgrade (September 29 – October 1, 2025) and published in a special edition as part of the project’s dissemination and outreach activities.

To continue engaging the community, in December 2024 CPN launched a second call for artistic projects for future roadshows and the 2025 Belgrade Festival, titled "*Navigating Climate: the Art of Big Data*". As seen previously throughout the Venice Festival, Art has proven to be an effective tool for engaging the public, including climate change professionals, and remains integral to our community engagement strategy. Artists and collectives were invited to explore the relationship between climate science and artistic expression. A total of **13 applications** were received from artists and groups based in the Netherlands, India, United States of America, United Kingdom, Bosnia and Herzegovina, France, Slovenia, Germany, Belgium, Georgia and Romania. Following a competitive selection process, one project was chosen to receive production support, artist fees, and a residency in Belgrade. The winning artist arrived in Belgrade within the reporting period, where he began developing the work in close collaboration with CPN and scientific experts from the CPN partners. The final piece is set to be presented at the Climateurope2 Festival in Belgrade in September 2025 and will be further showcased in other locations across Eastern and Southeastern Europe.

○ 4.4 Sessions and side events in other conferences

A number of major European conferences covering topics like climate change and climate adaptation are interesting venues for Climateurope2 to engage with new audiences and promote registration to the CE2 network. Some of the most relevant scientific conferences in this context are listed in Table 2.

Table 4. Conferences with relevance for the Climateurope2 network

Acronym	Full title	Schedule	Audience
ECCA	European Conference on Climate Change Adaptation	Every 2 years, 2025	Scientific and non-scientific climate adaptation community
EGU	European Geosciences Union	Yearly in April (Vienna)	Scientists in the Earth, planetary and space sciences
ESOF	EuroScience Open Forum	Every 2 years, 2025	Diverse audience - Scientists, Policy makers, Students, General public, etc.
EGI	EGI conference	Annual (Sep-Oct 2024)	international scientific communities, computing

			and service providers, European projects, security experts, community managers, and policymakers gathered
IEEE BigData24	IEEE International Conference on Big Data	December 2024	Researchers, practitioners, and professionals in big data analytics, machine learning, and related fields

In addition, CE2 project members attended a number of meetings. Here, a selection of relevant presentations:

In September - October 2024, researchers from UNITN and CMCC presented the talk “yProv: a Cloud-enabled Service for Multi-level Provenance Management And Exploration in Climate Workflows” at the EGI Conference in Lecce, Italy. The session highlighted advancements in provenance management for climate data workflows.

Later in December 2024, UNITN researchers contributed to the IEEE BigData24 Conference in Washington, DC, with the peer-reviewed paper and talk “Enabling Provenance Tracking in Workflow Management Systems” by L. Sacco, C. Sopranzetti, and S. Fiore.

In November 2024, at SuperComputing24 in Atlanta, GA, UNITN and CMCC jointly showcased their work in the paper and talk “A software ecosystem for multi-level provenance management in large-scale scientific workflows for AI applications” by G. Padovani et al.

These events have demonstrated their value in fostering community engagement, disseminating project updates, and showcasing results. WP6 intends to maintain its presence at these events in the future to sustain engagement and interaction.

5 Interaction with other projects

Some projects and institutions are explicitly mentioned in the grant agreement because of their relevance to several work packages (see Table 3).

Besides this, the consortium populated a longer list of relevant sister projects and initiatives, whose members can be invited to join the network (Table 4). Initial sister projects, funded for the Climate Adaptation Mission, were identified at project start, while later ones were identified through interactions, contacted to explore partnerships, exchange information, and increase visibility through website publication.

Continuously fostering external initiatives remains a core strategy for Climateurope2, aimed at strengthening community growth and enhancing engagement. A clear indicator of success lies in the comparison of network numbers before and after events, showcasing significant expansion. This approach, coupled with the utilisation of effective tools like engaging content, arts, and dissemination, positively contributes to the community's growth.

Table 5. Relevant projects from the Grant Agreement

Work package	Projects, programs and organisations	Audiences
WP1	Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures (TCFD)	Financial sector
	Standardisation organisations	Business community
WP2	IPCC AR6 and Data Distribution Center (DDC)	Researchers in climate change, adaptation and mitigation, policy makers and stakeholders
	ESA CCI - European Space Agency - Climate Change Initiative	Climate data producers
	IS-ENES3 - Infrastructure for the European Network for Earth System Modelling	Climate modellers, climate data producers and climate data users
	RDA - Research Data Alliance	Owners of climate data
WP4	MARCO - Market Research for a Climate services Observatory	Climate service providers
	EU-MACS - EUropean MArket for Climate Services	Climate service providers and users
	European Research Programmes including the EU Mission on Climate Adaptation and Societal Transformation	Wide range of researchers and research users
	Copernicus C3S	Climate service providers
	JPI Climate	Climate, adaptation and mitigation researchers

	GFDRR - Global Facility for Disaster Reduction and Recovery (World Bank)	Climate service users
WP5	ERA4CS	Climate data users, adaptation and mitigation researchers
WP6	CSP - Climate Services Partnership	Climate service providers
	GFCS - Global Framework for Climate Services (WMO)	Governments and organisations that produce and use climate information and services
WP8	EOSC- European Open Science Cloud	Climate data producers and data users
	HORIZON-CL3-2022-DRS-01-03 Horizon Topic Improved quality assurance / quality control of data used in decision-making related to risk management of natural hazards, accidents and CBRN events	Climate service providers
	HORIZON-CL4-2022-RESILIENCE-01-21 Horizon Topic Leveraging standardisation in Digital Technologies (CSA)	Standardisation community
	HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01-18 Horizon Topic Fostering standardisation to boost European industry's competitiveness (CSA)	Standardisation community
	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D2-01-13 Horizon Topic Strengthening Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) research communities in climate, energy and mobility disciplines	Climate service users
	HORIZON-MISS-2021-CLIMA-01-01 Horizon Topic Better prepared regional and local authorities to adapt to climate change	Climate service users
	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-03 Horizon Topic Maximising the impact	Climate service providers and users

	and synergy of European climate change research and innovation	
--	--	--

Table 6. Active Sister projects

Acronym	Full name and description	URL	Project coordination	Funding	End date
CLIMAAX	CLIMAtE risk and vulnerability Assessment framework and toolboX	https://www.climaax.eu/	Deltares. Project coordinator: Frederiek Sperna, Frederiek.SpernaWeiland@deltares.nl	Horizon RIA	31/12/2026
FutureMed	A transdisciplinary network to bridge climate science and impacts on society	https://www.cost.eu/actions/CA22162/	Technical University of Crete. Project coordinator: Aristeidis Koutroulis, akoutroulis@tuc.gr	COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology),	06/10/2027
IMPETUS	Turning climate commitments into action	https://climate-impetus.eu/	Eurecat	Horizon 2020	30/09/2025
IMPETUS 4 CHANGE	Improving near-term climate predictions for social transformation	https://impetus4change.eu/	i4c-pmo@norceresearch.no	Horizon Europe	31/10/2026
MAGICA	Maximising the synergy of European research governance and innovation for climate action	https://magica-project.eu/	Basque Centre for Climate Change (BC3). Project coordinator: María José Sanz mj.sanz@bc3research.org	Horizon 2020	31/5/26
MAIA	Maximising impact and accessibility of	https://maia-project.eu/	Fondazione Centro Euro-Mediterraneo	Horizon 2020	31/08/2025

	european climate research		sui Cambiamenti Climatici (CMCC) Project coordinator: Dr Giulia Galluccio, giulia.galluccio@cmcc.it		
VALORADA	Validated Local Risk Actionable Data for Adaptation	https://valorada-project.eu/	Dr. Cristobal Reveco Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon GmbH cristobal.reveco@hereon.de	Horizon Europe	31/05/2026

During the third and the fourth Webstivals we cooperated with PIISA; NATURANCE; CLIMATEFIT; SOTERIA IDAlert; CoSynHealth; AGORA, CLIMAAX, REACHOUT; IMPETUS4CHANGE, ICLEI,;

In addition, CE2 is part of the working group (WG) on climate services under the auspices of the Mission Implementation Platform (MIP4Adapt), which supports European regional and local authorities in their adaptation pathways to climate resilience. The WG brings together researchers and practitioners from 19 Horizon Europe projects funded under the EU Mission Adaptation, working together to understand and explore current approaches and challenges in upscaling climate services for adaptation in Europe.

6 Involvement of WPs in community engagement

Involving the climate services community is a shared effort that requires coordination within the Climateurope2 project. The community is critical for understanding standardisation needs and is therefore needed for providing information to key deliverables in, for example, WP1. Community members should experience a consistent approach across activities. To achieve this, effective internal communication is essential regarding the stakeholder engagement planned by each work package.

Climateurope2 includes 33 partners working across different work packages (WPs). To maintain effective communication and collaboration throughout the project, WP6 has created a cross-WP strategy. This strategy involves WP6 members regularly participating in meetings of other WPs (in addition to board meetings and WP1 to WP5 meetings) to stay updated on their activities and share information about their initiatives and activities. By doing so, WP6 encourages feedback and dialogue between WPs, helping to connect such a large consortium and promote teamwork. WP6 has developed a community-building roadmap encompassing both internal and external efforts (Figure 6). The internal roadmap emphasises coherent work and collaboration amongst WPs towards driving active community engagement. The external roadmap attracts new members and ensures that existing ones stay informed and engaged.

Figure 6. Community building roadmap: internal and external strategy

As shown in the figure above, the Climateurope2 consortium aims to attract more members to the community. Externally, the consortium shares existing materials such as infosheets and newsletters, and actively participates in external events rather than solely inviting potential members to attend Climateurope2's own events. The main strategy to attract new members is to clearly demonstrate the benefits they will receive by joining our network:

- Stakeholder engagement and **networking** (Climateurope2 hosts diverse activities and events, providing excellent opportunities to connect with the wide range of stakeholders)
- **Peer to Peer - P2P** (During these events, we extend invitations to various projects, allowing potential members to establish valuable connections in a project-to-project format)
- Be a part of a **great climate initiative** (Climateurope2 represents a project of over 30 partners which jointly work towards equitable and quality-assured CS for society)
- Exclusive Access to climate services Information: Members gain firsthand insights into climate services and standardisation, with interactive opportunities facilitated through the **Climateurope2 platform**.
- Joining the project's network provides access to both CE2 events and exclusive opportunities at external gatherings.

7 Methods to monitor progress of the network

The aim of the project is to expand the network beyond what was achieved in Climateurope, both in quantitative terms and in diversity. In order to achieve these goals, we monitor the progress to find out in what areas extra efforts are needed. In addition, we try to find out what methods and measures work, and if we need to try different alternatives for achieving diversity across the network, as well as equity and inclusion regarding the participation of network members in the project activities. Diversity can refer to personal characteristics such as age and gender, but also to geographic diversity across Europe and diversity in types of stakeholders (e.g. public and private, different economic sectors). In this update of the Climateurope2 engagement strategy, each method described will be considered and assessed according to its effectiveness.

The total number of community members is a Key Performance Indicator for WP6 (See Table 5 for the KPIs of WP6). The number of individuals participating in the network are monitored. Next to this, we acquire data on the size of the organisations they are part of, assuming that the knowledge they acquire will impact their organisations and thus increase the impact of the Climateurope2 project.

Table 7. WP6 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

KPI #	KPI description	KPI target
6.1	Number of stakeholders in the managed community	>300 in total
6.2	Attendees at the events organised to support the community (Festivals, Webstivals, roadshow)	>500
6.3	Overall satisfaction with the event assessed through evaluation form	More than 3.5 on average
6.4	Attendees at user perspectives webinar series	>300
6.5	Attendees to business breakfasts	>50

Methods we can use to track expanding the network progress are analysis of contact form interactions via the project website, feedback from stakeholders at events, surveys and interviews. Post-event surveys are planned after each of the events organised by Climateurope2. Monitoring diversity may involve sensitive personal data, which should be collected, managed and stored considering the GDPR guidelines.

Annex 1: Task 6.1 and Task 6.2 in Grant Agreement

Task 6.1 Establish, monitor and develop the European climate service network [M1-M50] (CPN lead, REH, WR, CMCC, Ecologic, RHMZ, SMHI, BSC, MetOffice)

Building on Climateurope's legacy and other activities (e.g. JPI-Climate/ERA4CS, C3S, CSP, GFCS, and the European Climate Pact), this task will **establish and monitor the Climateurope2 network**. The task will also **identify gaps in the diversity of the participants** of this European climate service network and develop a **strategy to improve the representation of different stakeholder typologies** from public and private sectors, reach a **greater inclusion from under-represented regions** (e.g. Eastern Europe) and **enhance the attainment of gender balance** across the network. A **concise live document describing the network status and including a Community Engagement Strategy will be available in M9 (D6.1)** and updated twice in the project lifetime to monitor the network evolution and engagement and adjust the strategy to reach low-represented and highly-relevant communities. This will include analysis of potential biases in the established community (e.g. gender and other biases). The data collected in WP6 will be analysed to understand the network dynamics and relevant results will be published for the benefit of the wider community including recommendations for the legacy and sustainability of the network beyond the project lifetime (D6.5).

Figure 7. Task 6.1 legend

Task 6.2: Engage with and organise events for the network [M3-50] (CMCC Lead, all WP6 partners)

In this task we will plan and organise the engagement and support activities and events to (a) bring the community together (face-to-face and virtually), (b) share knowledge amongst the community, including outputs of the project, and © build links across the climate services value chain to enhance end-to-end interaction. 1. Two Festivals in person (M18, M38) making use of large adaptation events (e.g. ECCA conference) to coordinate the project activities. 2. Six Webstivals (M6, M12, M24, M31, M45, M52) to stimulate a lively virtual conversation about multiple climate services domains. Project guidelines and recommendations will be presented for interactive processes of reflection to reinforce the feeling of co-ownership and wider dissemination. 3. A “Roadshow” (M10-M48) will bring the Festival idea to different nations to engage, build capacity and help drive action locally. We will engage with Copernicus Fora, local stakeholders and knowledge networks to export the outcomes of the project across Europe. We will promote the use of the project’s materials supporting local actors in the organisation of their own events. By doing so, we will promote an evolutionary and transformative capacity building about standards and processes in climate services. 4. At least two events (e.g. Business breakfasts) with standardisation, certification or other business stakeholders, organised by DNV. 5. At least two events organised by ECMWF discussing the main outcomes of the project relevant for C3S. During the project, WP6 partners and ECMWF will evaluate if these events are organised as a virtual stand-alone event or a session in a face-to-face event. 6.A Webinar series (M13-M54) will promote on-line discussions ensuring that network participants can share their voice and perspectives on the topics tackled. The scope of each event will adapt to the project evolution as more advanced outcomes are available to be discussed for feedback. The activities will target the breadth of the climate services community in Europe although they may focus on specific audiences depending on geographic locations, e.g. data-rich and data-scarce environments, coastal/ inland/ mountainous areas, and different sectors in society that will be involved (e.g urban development, agriculture, energy production, etc). Over the course of the project we aim to engage all sectors in need of climate services.

Figure 8. Task 6.2 legend

Table 8. WP6 Deliverables

Deliverable #	Deliverable title	Due month
D6.1	Community Engagement Strategy	M9 (delivered)
D6.2	First assessment of organised activities and first update to the community engagement strategy	M21
D6.3	Intermediate assessment of organised activities and second update to the community engagement strategy	M33

D6.4	Final assessment of organised activities and recommendations for future events	M46
D6.5	Recommendations for the future sustainability and improvement of the network and community, and the development of new forums based on lessons learnt	M50